

α -Picoline Complexes of the Cyanides, Thiocyanates, and Cyanates of Copper, Silver, and Mercury. Part I

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α -Picoline complexes of copper, silver, and mercury cyanates, thiocyanates, and cyanides have been prepared and analysed; properties of some of them have been studied. Compositions of the compounds are found to correspond to the following formulas: $\text{CuCN} : 2\text{Pic.}$, $\text{CuSCN} : 2\text{Pic.}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{CNO})_2 : 2\text{Pic.}$, $\text{AgCN} : 1\text{Pic.}$, $\text{AgSCN} : 1\text{Pic.}$, $\text{AgCNO} : 1\text{Pic.}$, $2\text{AgCNO} : 3\text{Pic.}$, $\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2 : 2\text{Pic.}$, $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2 : 1\text{Pic.}$, and $\text{Hg}(\text{CNO})_2 : 2\text{Pic.}$

Tombeck¹ reported the preparation of α -picoline complexes of AgCl , AgBr , AgI , AgCN , ZnI_2 , and CdBr_2 , as also of similar complexes with CuCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, CuSO_4 , and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)_2$. Garb² and Pesci³ prepared the α -picoline complexes of HgCl_2 and HgSO_4 , respectively. Luchowicz and Bandrowski⁴ prepared similar complexes with ZnCl_2 . Bhattacharya and Sinha⁵ have prepared and studied the α -picoline complexes of the thiocyanates and sulphates of Zn , Cd , Ni , and Co .

Tombeck¹ reported the preparation of the compound $\text{AgCN} : 2\text{Pic.}$ When an attempt was made in our laboratory to prepare the same compound under identical experimental conditions, the compound formed was $\text{AgCN} : 1\text{Pic.}$

In the present work α -picoline complexes of the cyanides, thiocyanates, and cyanates of copper, silver, and mercury have been prepared. The compositions of the complexes have been established by analysis and properties of some of them have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure chemicals, preferably of A.R. qualities of copper sulphate, sodium sulphite, silver nitrate, mercury oxide, potassium cyanide, potassium ferrocyanide, and potassium dichromate were recrystallised before use. α -Picoline was dried over KOH and freshly distilled.

CuCN , CuSCN , AgCN , AgSCN , AgCNO , $\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2$, $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2$, and KCNO were prepared in the laboratory and their purity was ascertained by analysis.

Copper(I) cyanide and thiocyanate were prepared by the methods of Berzelius⁶

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1800, *vis*, 21, 433; 22, 128.
2. *Gazette*, 1897, 27, 27.
3. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 15, 230.
4. *Monatsh.*, 1888, 9, 6175.
5. *This Journal*, 1955, 32, 317, 414.
6. Gmelin and Kraut, "Handbuch der anorg. Chem.", Band V, abt. I, p. 1013.

and Porret⁷; AgCN, AgSCN, and AgCNO by those of Sheele⁸, Porret⁸, and Wohler¹⁰; Hg(II) cyanide and thiocyanate by those of Rupp and Goy¹¹ and Peter¹², respectively.

A fresh sample of potassium cyanate was prepared in the laboratory by fusion of potassium ferrocyanide with potassium dichromate. The melt was cooled and powdered. The potassium cyanate was then extracted with a mixture of 80% EtOH and 10% MeOH.

All the α -picoline complexes of cyanides and thiocyanates of the above metals, other than that of mercury thiocyanate, were prepared in the following manner.

The cyanide or the thiocyanate (4-5 g.) was taken in a r.b. flask and to it pure, dried, and freshly distilled α -picoline (15-20 ml, b.p. 129°) was added and mixed thoroughly. This was then refluxed on a water bath for about 1-2 hours till nearly whole of the solid dissolved. In case of the preparation of the picoline complexes with silver salts, sunlight was avoided to prevent photochemical decomposition. The mixture was filtered hot to remove undissolved salts. The crystals of the complexes separated on cooling in the case of copper and slowly in the cases of silver and mercury. These were filtered, washed with pure picoline, and dried between the folds of filter paper.

Mercury(II) Thiocyanate-picoline Complex.—Mercury(II) thiocyanate is very highly soluble in α -picoline. The thiocyanate (5-6 g.) was taken in a stoppered flask and to it pure, dried, and freshly distilled α -picoline was added dropwise till almost all the solid had dissolved in it. The mixture was filtered to remove undissolved salt. Pure and dry ether was then added to the clear solution; the mixture was shaken and kept in a cool place. The complex separated in a crystalline form after sometime.

Silver Cyanate-picoline Complex.—Silver cyanate formed two complexes with α -picoline, the ratio of the ligand molecule to that of silver being 1:1 and 2:3 respectively. Both the compounds were of the same crystalline form.

The complex AgCNO: 1Pic. was prepared by refluxing AgCNO with the minimum quantity of α -picoline required to dissolve the solid. After filtering, crystals of the complex separated on cooling. These were recrystallised from chloroform.

The complex 2AgCNO: 3Pic. was prepared by dissolving the less picolinated complex in the excess of α -picoline. The crystals with higher picoline content were separated after keeping for a few days.

Picoline Complexes of Copper(II) and Mercury(II) Cyanates.—These compounds were prepared by the method of Davis and Logan¹³. The soluble metal salts (copper sulphate or mercuric nitrate) (5-6 g.) and an equivalent amount of KCNO were taken separately and dissolved in distilled water. The solutions were mixed and then pure, dried, and freshly distilled α -picoline was added till no further precipitation occurred. Thereafter pure and dried chloroform (200-300 ml) was added to dissolve the complex. The chloroform

7. "Handbuch der anorg. Chem.", Band V, abt. II, p. 150.

8. *Ibid.*, V, I, p. 1026.

9. *Ibid.*, V, II, p. 150.

10. *Gilb.*, 73, 168.

11. *Apoth.*, *Zeit.*, 1908, 23, 374.

12. *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3180.

13. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2493.

layer was separated and the solvent was evaporated when the crystals of the complexes were obtained.

Methods of Analysis.—Copper in the complexes was estimated volumetrically by iodometric titration; silver in the complexes was estimated as AgCl and mercury as HgS and HgZn (SCN)₄ (method of Lundell and Bee¹⁴).

In most cases estimation of picoline was carried out by the usual method of steam distillation in presence of excess of caustic alkali. The vapours of the picoline were absorbed in 2N-H₂SO₄. Difference in the titre values before and after the absorption of picoline provided the amount of the base. In the case of complexes of cyanates, this method could not be adopted directly as the cyanates hydrolysed very easily to ammonia; the titre values therefore provided the total amount of ammonia and picoline whereby the total nitrogen was calculated.

Again, the estimation of picoline could not be carried out in AgCN:1Pic. complex by the distillation method. Marsh and Struthers¹⁵ pointed out that AgCN reacted with alkali to provide metallic silver, potassium cyanide, and potassium cyanate. The potassium cyanate thus formed hydrolyses to ammonia which also distills with picoline. So here recourse was taken to the estimation of total nitrogen by Dumas' method.

Estimation of the anionic part of the complexes was carried out in the following way. Thiocyanates were converted into sulphates by boiling the complex with dilute nitric acid and the sulphates estimated as BaSO₄.

Estimation of cyanide in CuCN: 2Pic. was carried out by precipitating CN⁻ as AgCN and weighing as such. This method could not be adopted in Hg(CN)₂: 2Pic. complex owing to its non-electrolytic nature. So in this case the following method, as suggested by Rose, was followed.

To the aqueous solution of the complex was added about twice as much zinc sulphate in ammonia. The hydrogen sulphide water was added slowly to precipitate the HgS till upper layer showed a white precipitate of zinc sulphide. The precipitated sulphide was filtered and washed with a little ammonia. The filtrate contained all the cyanide. Cyanide was then precipitated by adding an excess of AgNO₃ and acidifying with an excess of dilute nitric acid.

The results of the analysis are recorded in Tables I-III. These complexes are found to have the following composition: CuCN: 2Pic., CuSCN: 2Pic., Cu(CNO)₂: 2Pic., AgCN: 1Pic., AgSCN :1Pic., AgCNO: 2Pic., 2AgCNO: 3Pic., Hg(CN)₂: 2Pic., Hg(SCN)₂: 1Pic., and Hg(CNO)₂: 2Pic. Properties of the complexes are reported in Table IV.

TABLE I
Cyanide complexes.

Contents.	CuCN : 2Pic.		AgCN : 1Pic.		Hg(CN) : 2Pic.	
	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Metal	22.90%	23.05%	47.33%	47.52%	45.20%	45.70%
CN ⁻	9.31	9.43	..	..	11.62	11.86
Picoline	67.10	67.52	..	..	43.18 (dif.)	42.43
Nitrogen	..	..	12.23	12.34	..	..

14. *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1914, 33, 987.

15. *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 18, 249.

TABLE II

Thiocyanate complexes.

Contents.	CuSCN : 2Pic.		AgSCN : 1Pic.		Hg(SCN) ₂ : 1Pic.	
	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Metal	20.79%	20.65%	41.30%	41.64%	48.70%	48.94%
SCN-	18.60	18.86	22.10	22.42	28.10	28.34
Picoline	60.75	60.49	35.50	35.94	22.90	22.72

TABLE III

Cyanate complexes.

Contents.	Cu(CNO) ₂ : 2Pic.		AgCNO : 1Pic.		2AgCNO : 3Pic.		Hg(CNC) ₂ : 2Pic.	
	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Metal	19.01%	19.04%	43.96%	44.39%	36.87%	37.25%	43.20%	42.60%
Nitrogen	17.05	16.78	11.47	11.52	11.97	12.09	11.76	11.90

N. B. Data mentioned above are the mean of three independent values.

TABLE IV

Properties.

Compounds.	Cryst. appearance.	Solubility.	Stability.	*Sp. gr.
CuCN : 2Pic.	White long needles changing to light yellow colour after some time.	Insoluble in water, ether, acetone, CCl ₄ , and CHCl ₃ . Sparingly soluble in toluene and EtOH.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° gradually decomposes giving off all its picoline.	1.41
CuSCN : 2Pic.	White long needles changing to light green colour after some time.	Insoluble in water, CHCl ₃ , ether, EtOH, and toluene. Sparingly soluble in benzene and acetone.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° decomposes giving off one molecule of picoline.	1.35
Cu(CNO) ₂ : 2Pic.	Bluish violet monoclinic crystals.	Soluble in CHCl ₃ and acetone producing blue solution and in MeOH forming green solution. Sparingly soluble in benzene, EtOH, toluene, and xylene. Insoluble in CCl ₄ and ether.	Stable at room temp. and at 50° decomposes gradually giving off all its picoline in about 12 days.	1.41
AgCN : 1Pic.	Colorless prismatic crystals.	Insoluble in CCl ₄ , benzene, MeOH, CHCl ₃ , and ether. Sparingly soluble in water, EtOH, and acetone.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° decomposes.	1.37
AgSCN : 1Pic.	White needles.	Insoluble in water, CHCl ₃ , benzene, and CCl ₄ . Sparingly soluble in acetone, EtOH, and ether.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° decomposes giving off all its picoline in about 14 days.	1.37

TABLE IV (contd.)

Compounds.	Cryst. appearance.	Solubility.	Stability.	*Sp. gr.
AgCNO : 1 Pic.	Colorless prismatic crystals.	Soluble in CHCl_3 . Partially soluble in acetone and hot water. Sparingly soluble in EtOH, MeOH, and cold water. Insoluble in toluene, ether, CCl_4 , and benzene.	Stable at room temp. and at 50° decomposes giving off all its picoline in about 6 days.	2.11
2AgCNO: 3 Pic.	Colorless prismatic crystals.	Partially soluble in acetone. Insoluble in toluene and CCl_4 . Sparingly soluble in EtOH, MeOH, CHCl_3 , benzene, and water.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° decomposes.	1.48
$\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2$: 2Pic,	White long needles,	Moderately soluble in water and EtOH. Very readily soluble in acetone. Sparingly soluble in xylene, benzene, ether, toluene, and CHCl_3 . Insoluble in CCl_4 .	Stable at room temp. but at 50° gradually decomposes giving off all its picoline in about 48 hours.	1.37
$\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2$: 2Pic.	Colorless cubic crystals.	Moderately soluble in acetone and EtOH. Partially soluble in water. Sparingly soluble in CHCl_3 . Insoluble in benzene, ether, toluene, xylene, and CCl_4 .	Stable at room temp. but at 50° decomposes giving off all its picoline in about 6 days.	1.41
$\text{Hg}(\text{CNO})_2$: 2Pic.	Colorless monoclinic crystals.	Very readily soluble in MeOH and acetone. Soluble in water, CHCl_3 , EtOH, ether, xylene, and toluene.	Stable at room temp. but at 50° gradually decomposes giving off all its picoline.	..

*Sp. gravity was determined by sp. gravity bottle.